

Hybrid Provision of Energy based on Reliability and Resiliency by Integration of Dc Equipment

Work Package WP5

Open and secure ICT for modular resilient optimized hybrid grid

Deliverable D5.6

Open HYPERRIDE ICT platform (preliminary version)

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List of Abbreviations

AC	Alternating Current
ADS	Anomaly Detection System
API	Application Programming Interface
CB	Context Broker
DC	Direct Current
EC	European Commission
GE	Generic Enabler
GEs	Generic Enablers
GUI	Graphical User Interface
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IdM	Identity Manager
IDS	Intrusion Detection System
IoT	Internet of Things
LD	Linked Data
MQTT	Message Queue Telemetry Transport
NGSI	Next Generation Service Interface
PEP	Policy Enforcement Point
PDP	Policy Decision Point
PoC	Proof of Concept
SIEM	Security Information and Event Management
XDR	Extended Detection and Response

Executive Summary

ICT plays a crucial role in smart grid, ensuring a secure and reliable communication and control of all smart grid elements. In this perspective, the HYPERRIDE Open ICT platform is positioned. The high-level overview of the platform architecture was given in deliverable D5.1 (Mamma et al., 2021). It comprises three horizontal layers, namely:

- The Presentation Layer, which is responsible for handling all user interface and browser communication logic.
- The Knowledge Layer, which represents the underlying domain, mostly consisting of context information and data.
- The Acquisition and Interoperability Layer, which main role is to capture data from different devices and, when requested, to convert those data in standardised context information.

An additional cross-cutting Security Layer is responsible for all concerns related to security, both cyber and physical. This latter Security Layer has been later enhanced with the addition of a Security Monitoring System component that unifies Extended Detection and Response and Security Information and Event Management capabilities, including log data analysis, intrusion and malware detection, file integrity monitoring, vulnerability detection. Details are provided in the deliverable D5.3.

In this document, a brief overview of the ICT architecture and its enhancement are given and users are guided to the installation and use of a preliminary version of the Platform.

Moreover, a Proof of Concept (PoC) has been designed, developed, and made available within this preliminary version of the Open ICT Platform. The main purpose of the PoC is to demonstrate the feasibility of the current solution, its functionalities, and to provide at the same time a reference for the developer for the exploitation of the ICT Platform Application Programming Interface (API) and tools.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

The HYPERRIDE project aims to design and implement an open and secure information communication technology ICT Platform capable to support new services to set up and manage AC/DC grids. The ICT Platform enables:

- the seamless integration and management of devices, regardless of how smart they are;
- scalable and interoperable collection and management of data that support near real time observability and optimisation of the operation of modular and resilient hybrid AC/DC grids;
- the transmission of commands or setpoints for the safe and reliable operation of the grid;
- detection, prediction, prevention of technical and cyber contingencies.

1.2 Structure of the Document

This document is organised as follows: Section 2 describes the HYPERRIDE Open ICT Platform architecture and provides the installation and usage guidelines references, Section 3 describes a PoC that proves the feasibility of the solution proposed for the platform, Section 4 gives conclusions.

1.3 Intended Audience

The intended audience of this document is represented by the members of the HYPERRIDE consortium and European Commission (EC) representatives tasked with reviewing the project and its progress towards meeting the specified milestones. HYPERRIDE stakeholders may use this document to evaluate the adequacy of the HYPERRIDE ICT Platform from the perspective of their individual areas of expertise.

1.4 Relations to Other Activities

The requirement elicitation process and analysis and the HYPERRIDE ICT Platform design, conducted in Task 5.1 and reported in D5.1, and the refinement of the ICT Platform architecture for the detection and prediction of technical and cyber-contingencies, conducted in T5.3 and reported in D5.3, have been used as a basis for the implementation and installation in Task 5.6 of the preliminary version of the Platform, which is reported in this document, accompanying report of D5.6 Open HYPERRIDE ICT platform (preliminary version). This document will be a valid support for the enhancement of the ICT Platform that will be released as deliverable D5.8 Open HYPERRIDE ICT platform (final version) and adequately documented in the related accompanying report.

2 Open ICT Platform

2.1 Software Architecture

The HYPERRIDE project aims to design and implement an Open ICT Platform enabling:

- the seamless integration and management of devices, regardless of how smart they are;
- scalable and interoperable collection and management of data that support near real time observability and optimisation of the operation of modular and resilient hybrid AC/DC grids;
- the transmission of commands/setpoints for the safe and reliable operation of the grid;
- detection, prediction, prevention of technical and cyber-contingencies.

The HYPERRIDE ICT Platform architecture and integrated tools were introduced in D5.1 (Mammaia et al., 2021). This deliverable documents the results of the activities conducted in HYPERRIDE aiming at the elicitation and analysis of functional and non-functional requirements of the Platform and provide the high-level design of the Platform architecture in terms of static and dynamic behaviour of the system. The high-level view of the HYPERRIDE ICT Platform architecture and integrated tools, depicted in Figure 1, comprises three horizontal layers, namely:

- The Presentation Layer, which implements the functionalities required to allow users to interact with the system, handling all user interface and browser communication logic;
- The Knowledge Layer, which represents the underlying domain, mostly consisting of context information and data;
- The Acquisition and Interoperability Layer, which captures data from different devices and, when requested, to convert those data in standardised context information.

An additional cross-cutting Security Layer is responsible for cyber and physical security aspects: from the cyber point of view, it provides authenticated and authorised access to the system resources, while from the physical point of view, it supports situation awareness and provides insights about the root cause of the events and alerts generated by the tools that are responsible for continuous monitoring of the system behaviour.

As explained in D5.1 (Mammaia et al., 2021), the Platform leverages on FIWARE Context Broker (CB) Generic Enabler (GE), which manages the entire lifecycle of context information including updates, queries, registrations, and subscriptions. The Identity Manager Identity Manager (IdM) GE, the Policy Enforcement Point (PEP) GE, and the Policy Decision Point (PDP) GE are in charge for managing the identities and the related security aspects. The Internet of Things (IoT) Agents Generic Enablers (GEs) are components, present in the FIWARE catalogue (*FIWARE catalogue*, n.d.), that lets a group of devices send their data to and be managed from a CB using their own native protocols; if the needed IoT Agents are not in the catalogue, custom IoT Agents can be implemented using the libraries made available by FIWARE. Further details are provided in D5.1.

In the deliverable D5.3, report devoted to technical and cyber contingencies prediction and detection in HYPERRIDE, the architecture of the platform has been enriched in its Security Layer with a Securing Monitoring System component, that is the free and open-source security platform Wazuh (Figure 2), which unifies Extended Detection and Response (XDR) and Security Information and Event Management (SIEM) capabilities, including log data analysis, intrusion and malware detection, file integrity monitoring, vulnerability detection. The Wazuh architecture

Figure 1: HYPERRIDE Open ICT Platform Architecture and Integrated Tools [D5.1].

is based on the Wazuh Server, the Wazuh Indexer, and the Wazuh Dashboard, but also on the Wazuh Agents, which are deployed on the monitored endpoints and provides threat prevention, detection, and response capabilities. Further details are provided in D5.3.

Figure 2: HYPERRIDE Open ICT Platform Architecture extended with the Security Monitoring System [D5.3].

The Figure 3 provides a complete view of the ICT Platform and the systems it controls (on the bottom side) and the services that will be implemented in the context of HYPERRIDE and that will made use of data acquired through the ICT Platform (on the left side).

In this document D5.6 will be provided the instructions and usage guidelines for the preliminary set-up of the main components of the HYPERRIDE ICT Platform. The preliminary architecture consists of the following components (Figure 4):

- FIWARE Orion CB, which will receive requests using NGSI-v2 (*Welcome To Orion Context Broker*, n.d.) or NGSI-LD (*FIWARE context.Orion-LD*, n.d.);

Figure 3: Overarching view of the HYPERRIDE Open ICT Platform, the systems it controls, and the HYPERRIDE AC/DC services.

- FIWARE Keyrock (FIWARE, 2021a), which is an Identity Management System including:
 - An OAuth2 authentication system for Applications and Users;
 - A site graphical frontend for Identity Management Administration;
 - An equivalent REST API for Identity Management via HTTP requests.
- FIWARE Wilma (FIWARE, 2021b), which is a PEP Proxy securing access to Orion and/or IoT Agent microservices;
- The underlying MongoDB database:
 - Used by the Orion CB to hold context data information such as data entities, subscriptions, and registrations;
 - Used by the IoT Agent to hold device information such as device URLs and Keys.
- A MySQL database, which is used to persist user identities, applications, roles, and permissions;
- The HYPERRIDE Services, which will be implemented in the context of WP4;
- IoT Agents present in the FIWARE catalogue or custom (*iotagent-node-lib Architecture*, n.d.).

Such components fulfil the main functionalities of the Platform in terms of management of the identities, management of data, and actual authentication and optional authorisation checks. Instructions for a complete installation of the platform, with the integration of HYPERRIDE AC/DC services and systems to monitor/control in a real field, will be documented in D5.8 Open HYPERRIDE ICT platform (final version) accompanying report. The final platform release will include any improvements related to findings and recommendations from the penetration tests.

Figure 4: HYPERRIDE Open ICT Platform - Preliminary Architecture.

2.2 Installation and Usage Guide

A guide for the installation and the usage of the ICT Platform and its API is available in GitHub. This must be considered as integrant part of the deliverable. Please, refer to the links in the following paragraph.

2.3 Associated Outputs

The work described in this deliverable has resulted in the following resources:

Table 1: Associated Outputs chapter 2.

Description	URL	Availability
Software	https://github.com/engsep/HYPERRIDE .	Public
Guide	https://github.com/engsep/HYPERRIDE/blob/main/README.md .	Public
Mirror	https://github.com/engsep/HYPERRIDE/tree/D5.6	Public

3 Proof of Concept

3.1 Description

As part of the current deliverable, a PoC has been designed, developed and made available within this ICT Platform release. The main purpose of the PoC is to demonstrate the feasibility of the current solution, its functionalities, and to provide at the same time a reference for the developer for the exploitation of the ICT Platform API and tools.

The PoC has been designed integrating the platform with a few devices to get results about platform functionalities in a straightforward way. Indeed, the PoC includes a simulated demo site only with two temperature sensors sending data via Message Queue Telemetry Transport (MQTT) protocol. It has been assumed that the two temperature sensors are connected to electric devices to monitor their working status and report anomalies. The ICT Platform is connected to the sensors, receiving the appropriate MQTT topics from the sensors, by means of the Node-RED IoT Agent configured for the PoC. The Agent works as a wrapper between the sensors and the FIWARE CB. Two versions of CB have been implemented within the ICT Platform, Orion v2 and Linked Data (LD). For this demo, v2 has been used.

The FIWARE CB continuously receive Next Generation Service Interface (NGSI) entities, provided by the Node-RED IoT Agent on the basis of the received measurements. To complete the demo, a simple Anomaly Detection System (ADS) has been implemented as well. The ADS is subscribed to the CB to receive NGSI entities with type "TemperatureSensor", and guesses possible anomalies with a very simple rule-based system: if the temperature is much lower than the ambient temperature it consider the device associated to the temperature as possibly off, while if its temperature is higher than another set upper threshold it considers a possible shortcut inside the electrical device. The corresponding information is sent back to the CB in terms of another NGSI Entity, of type "Event", category "anomaly". This completes all the possible exploitation of the ICT Platform, for all kind of operations, reading, writing and subscriptions.

All the operations are made in a secure way, mediated by IdM and PEP Proxy: any attempt of using the ICT Platform with wrong credentials and/or token results in an error caught and registered by a Intrusion Detection System (IDS) which produces, in its turn, NGSI Entities of type "Event" and category "intrusion", and sent to the CB for any subscriber interested.

To complete the demo, an MQTT topic is written for any received event to inform third party or external services about intrusion or anomaly detections. E.g., the REASENS tool from AIT can be informed in this way to run its evidential network for the root cause analysis. Please refer to D5.3 for any further detail about.

3.2 Graphical User Interface

The PoC is publicly available at the link reported in the next paragraph. It has been deployed as Node-RED Dashboard in the cloud for demonstration purposes. No installation is required. No credentials are needed to access it.

The Graphical User Interface (GUI) has been designed to be simple and easy to use, as the concept of the PoC as well. For this reasons, it consists of a single page, with all the sections visualized, including the Keyrock IdM login one. Of course, in a production environment, for real-world application, this section would not be shown, especially the access token, but for the

purpose of the demo, it is shown to make intentional attempts of simulated possible attacks (such as brute force, with wrong credentials or token).

The GUI of the PoC is shown in (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Reference Implementation - Proof of Concept.

In the Monitoring Layer frame, the user can select and send the temperatures of the simulated temperature sensors manually through the sliders and the "Send" button. Alternatively, the automatic generation can be started with the switch "Auto". Historical data are also plotted, including the two thresholds for the anomaly detection.

In the Security Layer frame, the user can input the Keyrock user credentials (see GitHub for the correct default ones) and generate a new token, for the demo purpose. The "Refresh" button is used to restart the Node-RED flows from scratch (mainly for debug purposes).

In the Context Broker frame, the Orion CB is shown and the registered NGSI entities listed. Two buttons are available, "FIWARE Lab" to use the default version of the ICT Platform deployed for the demo pupose, and "Gitpod" to start an ephemeral environment with a new instance of the ICT Platform built from scratch. A free Gitpod account is needed.

In the Intrusion Detection and Anomaly Detection frame, all the security events are logged. In particular, a green or red led is shown for the intrusions, and a table of possible identified issues is shown for the anomalies,

3.3 Associated Outputs

The work described in this deliverable has resulted in the following resources:

Table 2: Associated Outputs chapter 3.

Description	URL	Availability
PoC	https://hyperride.engsep.repl.co/	Public

4 Conclusions

The role of ICT is to ensure a secure and reliable communication and control of all smart grid elements. In this perspective, the HYPERRIDE Open ICT platform is positioned. In the previous HYPERRIDE D5.1 and D5.3 deliverables, the architecture of the Open ICT Platform has been sketched and subsequently improved. For convenience, in Section 2, the architecture and its improvements have been briefly presented and installation and user guidelines of a preliminary version of the platform have been given. In Section 3, a PoC has been designed and implemented to demonstrate the feasibility of the current platform solution and its functionalities. The PoC consists of a simulated demo site, extremely simplified, with two temperature sensors sending data via Message Queue Telemetry Transport (MQTT) protocol. A FIWARE Context Broker receive continuously NGSI entities, provided by a Node-RED IoT Agent on the basis of the received measurements. A simple ADS is subscribed to the CB to receive NGSI measure from sensors and guesses possible anomalies with a very simple rule-based system. All the operations are made in a secure way, mediated by IdM and PEP Proxy: any attempt of using the ICT Platform with wrong credentials and/or token results in an error caught and registered by an IDS, which, in its turn, notifies it to the CB for any subscriber interested. To complete the demo, an MQTT topic is written for any received event to inform third party or external services about intrusion or anomaly detections.

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